

length of analysis (1 1/2-2 h) and the relatively large sample size (50 g) severely limited the number of tests that could be performed and the generation of the breeding program to which it could be applied.

The R.V.A. analysis uses a smaller sample (3 g) and is much quicker. By selecting a heating rate, cooking time, and cooling rate proportional to, but much faster than, the Visco-Amylograph, it is possible to obtain similar information.

The heating/cooling computer program allows wide variability. The initial temperature can be set at 0-100°C, with a hold delay of any number of minutes. Heating rates of 0-20°C/min in two independent ramps, with an optional hold period between the ramps, are possible. Cooking at the top temperature can be maintained for any period before cooling at 0-20°C/min to the initial temperature.

The figure shows the curves obtained when flour from three samples of rice

with different amylose content were heated, cooked, and cooled under different sets of parameters. The flour slurries (3 g/25 ml) were heated and cooled at rates of 3, 6, and 12°C/min, with cooking times at 95°C of 10, 5, and 2.5 min, respectively.

When the R.V.A. is programmed at heating and cooling rates of 12°C/min, the complete testing cycle takes only 11 min and produces viscosity curves very similar to those produced using a conventional Amylograph with a heating rate of 1.5°C/min. To obtain similar viscosity curves, it appears necessary to combine precise control of heating rate with the amount of shear that the testing instrument imparts to the starch slurry.

The R.V.A. viscosity curves adequately discriminate between rices with different textural properties. Its ability to process small samples will allow data on paste viscosity to be obtained from earlier generations and many more samples. The modified R.V.A. has the added advantage that data acquisition, analysis, and comparison with standard varietal samples are done automatically, and appear on the computer screen. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Genetics of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in two land races of rice from India

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We studied the inheritance of resistance to Indian pathotype IXO5 of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* in two land races of rice, ARC 10464 and CNGS20083. The land races were crossed with susceptible Taichung Native 1 (TN1) and among themselves. The F₂s from resistant/susceptible and resistant/resistant crosses were transplanted at 40 d after seeding in 3-m-long rows, 50 cm apart.

Curves obtained when 3-g samples of rice flour were processed in a computer-controlled Rapid Visco Analyser.

Plants were inoculated 30 d after transplanting with a 48-h-old culture of pathotype IXO5, by clipping method. The bacterial concentrations were maintained at 10^6 - 10^8 cells/ml. Pathotype IXO5 is virulent to genes *Xa*-1, *Xa*-3, *Xa* (Ka), *Xa*-4, *Xa*-5, *Xa*-9, and *Xa*-10; lines carrying genes *Xa*-2, *Xa*-6, *Xa*-7, and *Xa*-11 show moderate resistance.

Level of resistance was determined by lesion length in centimeters on three inoculated leaves 14 d after inoculation: resistant (R) = mean lesion length less than 25% of that on TN1; moderately resistant (MR) = mean lesion length 26-50% that of TN1; susceptible (S) = mean lesion length greater than 50% that of TN1. To compute genetic ratios, R and MR plants were grouped as resistant.

Segregation patterns in different F_2 s are given in the table. The F_2 from the cross ARC10464/TN1 segregated in a

Mean lesion length on parents and segregation for BB resistance in F_2 from different crosses.

Parent, cross	Resistant		Susceptible		Ratio	χ^2 value
	Plants (no.)	Mean lesion length (cm)	Plants (no.)	Mean lesion length (cm)		
ARC10464	10	1.32	-	-	-	-
CNGS20083	10	1.48	-	-	-	-
TN1	-	-	10	10.10	-	-
ARC10464/TN1	178	3.23	15	8.16	15:1	0.76
CNGS20083/TN1	63	2.00	161	9.05	1:3	1.16
ARC10464/CNGS20083	90	3.15	3	9.15	61:3	0.49

15R:1S ratio, suggesting the presence of two independently inherited dominant genes in ARC10464. The F_2 from CNGS20083/TN1 segregated in a 1R:3S ratio, suggesting the presence of a recessive gene. The F_2 from the cross of the two resistant lines segregated in a 61R:3S ratio, confirming the presence of two dominant genes in ARC10464 and a recessive gene in CNGS20083.

ARC10464 is a semidwarf type; CNGS20083, a tall rice with very poor plant type. ARC10464 is not resistant to all the pathotypes of BB reported from India; CNGS20083 is resistant to all the BB pathotypes. Use of such lines with simple genetic control of resistance in breeding programs could help improve resistance of new varieties. □

Pest resistance–insects

Screening of rice varieties and advanced breeding lines in Cambodia for resistance to gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae*

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We screened 907 varieties and advanced breeding lines being tested in Observational Yield Trials (early, medium, mixed, and late), the International Irrigated Rice Observational Nursery, and the International Rice Lowland Observational Nursery, during a serious GM outbreak in 1990 wet season.

Entries were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing, one seedling/hill in field plots. GM damage was scored at the maximum tillering to heading stage. Damage on hill basis considered all hills in a plot; damage on tiller basis was evaluated on 20 randomly selected hills per plot. Percentages of infested hills and

Table 1. Varieties showing resistance to GM on hill as well as tiller basis.

Variety	Infestation				Origin
	Hill		Tiller		
	%	Score	%	Score	
174 BAA	10	3	5	3	Tanzania
79007-TR7-40-4-1-1	5	1	5	3	Turkey
7901-TR16-1-1	0	0	0	0	Turkey
7906-TR11-1-1	0	0	0	0	Turkey
80023-TR166-2-1-4	5	1	4	3	Turkey
80055-TR198-5-1-1	5	1	5	3	Turkey
Badshabhog (Acc 285431)	10	3	4	3	Bangladesh
Chhuthana 1-078-1-1-1-1	4	1	3	3	Cambodia
Chhuthana 1-078-3-1-1-2	4	1	2	3	Cambodia
Dunasan	0	0	0	0	China
Hua Lien Yu164	5	1	4	3	Taiwan
HURI 370	0	0	0	0	Hungary
HURI 386	0	0	0	0	Hungary
IB 15B	0	0	0	0	Burundi
IB 15C	0	0	0	0	Burundi
IB 17	0	0	0	0	Burundi
IB 28	0	0	0	0	Burundi
IB 33	0	0	0	0	Burundi
IB 44	0	0	0	0	Burundi
IR35366-28-3-1-2-2	5	1	3	3	IRRI
IR41996-50-2-1-3	10	3	5	3	IRRI
IR51079-35-2-3-3-3	4	1	3	3	IRRI
IR51130-SKN-24-B-1-5-1	0	0	0	0	IRRI
IR51130-SKN-31-B-1-6-1	2	1	3	3	IRRI
IR51640-153-1-2-2	5	1	3	3	IRRI
IR52256-190-2-2-1	10	3	5	3	IRRI
IR53901-14-1-1-2	5	1	3	3	IRRI
IRS6381-155-1-2-2	10	3	2	3	IRRI
IR59081-CPA-2-B-1-2	0	0	0	0	IRRI
Kankai 12-11-84	10	3	3	3	Nepal
Khao Pong Krai	0	0	0	0	Thailand
Mahsuri	8	3	5	3	Malaysia
Neang Mon 1-027-3-1-1-2	0	0	0	0	Cambodia
ORC	0	0	0	0	Chile
Quella-Inia	5	1	3	3	Chile
RD 27	10	3	3	3	Thailand
RP1057-391-1	10	3	5	3	India
RP2107-14-12	10	3	4	3	India
Somaly 2-023-3-5-1-2-1	4	1	4	3	Cambodia
Somaly 2-023-6-2-2-1-1	4	1	2	3	Cambodia